

A NOVEL ROUTE FOR PREPARATION OF NANOSTRUCTURED CARBON GOLD COMPOSITE BALL FROM ARBORESCENT COPOLYMER MICELLES

M. Huh^{1,2}, M. Jung¹, W. Ki¹, S. Kang¹, M. Gauthier³, S. Yun^{1*}

¹ Jeonju Institute of Machinery and Carbon composites, Jeonju 561-844, Korea

² Department of Polymer Nano Science and Technology, Chonbuk National University, Jeonju 561-756, Korea

³ Department of Chemistry, Institute for Polymer Research, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario N2L 3G1, Canada

* Corresponding author(ysi@jmc.re.kr)

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1 Introduction

Carbonaceous materials have been employed as catalyst support, separation medium, energy storage and conversion system. Pyrolysis of ordered micelles on the substrate leads to stable carbon ball or nano-patterned carbon materials¹⁻². In contrast to conventional micelles, dendritic micelles retain much more stable morphology due to their covalently bonded structures³.

In the studies, UV irradiation effectively cross-link the PS core / P2VP shell and heating at 600 °C leads to a highly stable carbon ball or nano-patterned carbon materials. Highly reactive P2VP shell can readily incorporate Au nanoparticles (NPs), which lead to carbon/Au hybrid. The subsequent UV treatment and annealing lead to carbon/Au composite ball.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of core-shell morphology.

2 Experimental Section

Materials. The synthesis of the arborescent P2VP copolymers used in this study has been discussed in detail elsewhere. The M_n of the side chains was determined by size exclusion chromatography analysis of samples removed from the reactor prior to the grafting reactions. A twice-grafted arborescent polystyrene(G1PS), containing 205 side chains with $M_n = 4900(5K)$ and having a total $M_n = 1.1 \times 10^6$, served as grafting substrate for the preparation of both copolymers. The characteristics of the P2VP copolymers are summarized in Table 1.

Preparation. The micelles were deposited on silicon wafers through spin coating of solutions containing 1 wt% PS-b-P2VP in selective solvents. UV irradiation was used to induce cross-linking of the PS core in the micelles. After pyrolysis, both the PS and the P2VP were converted into carbonaceous materials.

Atomic force microscope(AFM). Surface morphology of the micelles and carbon ball were observed by AFM nanoscope IV multimode (Digital Instrument, MicroMash Co., USA) in tapping mode using Si cantilever with a spring constant of 305N/m and a resonance frequency of 75kHz. Scanning was performed at scan speed of 1.85Hz.

Scanning Electron Microscopy(SEM). The formation of carbon material was confirmed by scanning electron microscopy(SEM, operated on Heachi S-4700 microscopy)

Transmission Electron Microscopy(TEM). The formation of Au nanoparticles were investigated by

transmission electron microscopy(TEM, operated with EM 912 Omega).

Table 1. Characteristics for G1PS-P2VP copolymer^a.

Sample	$M_n^b/P2VP_{branch} \times 10^3$	$f_n^d/P2VP_{branch}$	P2VP, mol%	M_n^c
G1PS-P2VP5K	6.2	1180	87	8.4×10^6

^a 2VP polymerization in THF at -78°C and grafting at room temperature.

^b Absolute Mn of P2VP chains determined by SEC-MALLS analysis.

^c Values determined by combining the absolute Mn of the substrate with copolymer composition from 1H NMR analysis.

^d Number of P2VP branches added in the last grafting reaction.

Fig. 2. Preparation of carbon/gold nanoparticles composites

3 Results & Discussion

Fig 3. shows an atomic force microscopy (AFM) image of PS-P2VP micelle films (prepared from PS-P2VP / THF solutions with the copolymer concentration of 1 %). The highly ordered thin nanostructured films consisting of PS-P2VP can be seen. Thin film treated water was treated directly by converted to likewise nanostructured carbon films with engineered surface topographies. After pyrolysis, cross-linked micelles were decreased of particle size.

Fig 4. shows an atomic force microscopy (AFM) image of micelle films prepared from PS-P2VP / methanol solutions with the copolymer concentration of (a) 0.1, (b) 0.25, (c) 1 %. Depending on the copolymer concentration increased coating thickness,

the highly ordered nanostructure of micelle films had disappeared.

Fig 3. PS-P2VP micelle films(prepared from PS-P2VP / THF solutions with the copolymer concentration of 1 %) prior to after carbonization at 600 °C. (a) nanopatterned film, (b) H₂O-treated films prior to carbonization, (c) carbonaceous film.

Fig 5. shows a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of PS-P2VP / PS-P2VP micelle films (prepared from PS-P2VP/THF solutions with the copolymer concentration 1%) prior to and after carbonization at 600 °C . After pyrolysis of nanopatterned film, thickness of carbonaceous film was reduction by more than 34% compared to before.

Fig. 4. Nanopatterned films prepared from PS-P2VP / methanol solutions with the copolymer concentration of (a) 0.1, (b) 0.25, (c) 1 %.

Fig. 6. Shows UV-vis absorption spectra and TEM image of nanopatterned films. Transmission electron micrographs (TEM) images and UV spectroscopy were confirmed an synthesis of Au nanoparticles . The dark species have been identified as small gold nanoparticles, which formed upon electron irradiation in the TEM by reduction of the tetrachloroaurate. Clearly, the gold particles arranged in clusters where a cluster corresponded to the core of a micelle.

Fig. 5. PS-P2VP micelle films(prepared from PS-P2VP/THF solutions with the copolymer concentration 1%) prior to and after carbonization 600 °C. (a) nanopatterned film, (b) carbonaceous film.

Fig. 6. (a) TEM images of gold NP(nanoparticles). (b) UV-vis absorption spectra of arborescent

copolymer G1PS-P2VP5K before (dashed line) and after (solid line) the immobilization of Au NP.

4 Conclusion

The highly ordered thin nanostructured films consisting of PS-P2VP can directly be converted to likewise nanostructured carbon films with engineered surface topographies. The Au nanoparticles were synthesized by NaBH₄ reduction of HAuCl₄ salt in the presence of PS-P2VP copolymer, and the interaction of nanoparticle precursors with pyridyl rings of the P2VP chains has been exploited as the driving force for the immobilization process.

References

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